

**make
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Deliverable D3.2
Impact
Assessment Plan

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Revision of History

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MAT	make-a-thek
NEB	New European Bauhaus Festival
No	Number of
OD	OpenDot
OER	Open Educational Resources
ORL	Organisational Readiness Level
SRL	Societal Readiness Level
TRL	Technological Readiness Level
UMA	Ukrainian Makerspace Association
WP	Work Package
WS	Workshop
ZSI	Center for Social Innovation

Executive Summary

This **Impact Assessment Plan (Deliverable D3.2)** presents the evaluation and impact assessment strategy for *make-a-thek*, a Horizon Europe Innovation Action (Grant Agreement No. 101177660) titled “*Modular Library Makerspaces for Heritage Crafts Innovation and Digitization.*”

The Impact Assessment Plan provides a comprehensive framework to **evaluate the project’s outputs, outcomes and long-term societal impact**. It pursues two main objectives:

1. **Formative evaluation** – ensuring that project activities, infrastructures, and networks develop effectively and align with the overall objectives; and
2. **Summative evaluation** – demonstrating the project’s tangible impact on individuals, organisations, and communities.

The plan introduces a logic-model-based indicator framework linking project activities, outputs, outcomes, and impacts. It connects quantitative and qualitative evidence across all work packages to assess the uptake and societal relevance of the *make-a-thek* approach, where public libraries become a place for circular economy experience and co-creation focused on fashion and crafts. Based on this plan, effects on awareness, knowledge, skills and behaviour of the involved stakeholders are investigated. Indicators are tailored to the needs of participating libraries, makers, crafters, fashion and circularity experts, and citizens, with regular reflection and adaptation throughout the project lifecycle.

Evaluation tools include **feedback cards, questionnaires, target evaluations, graffiti walls, semi-structured impact interviews, focus group discussions, and internal reporting**. The data from these evaluation instruments are collected, translated, analysed and collaboratively reflected within the project team. Together, these instruments capture both measurable results and personal experiences of learning, collaboration, and behavioural change.

Complementary to these, the project applies **Societal Readiness Levels (SRL)** and **Organisational Readiness Levels (ORL)** to track the social adoption of the *make-a-thek* approach and the preparedness of pilot libraries for long-term integration. The expected progression is from SRL 2–3 to SRL 5–6 and from ORL 2–3 to ORL 5–6 by project end.

Ethical and data-protection principles are embedded throughout. All data collection follows informed consent and GDPR-compliant procedures, with anonymised and securely stored records.

The evaluation follows three phases:

- **Co-creation phase (Year 1):** Defining stakeholder expectations and impact metrics.

- **Implementation phase (Year 2):** Gathering evidence from pilot libraries and the mobile make-a-thek bus.
- **Scale-up and reflection phase (Year 3):** Assessing scalability and policy relevance in Europe and beyond.

This plan ensures that *make-a-thek* meets its internal project objectives, creates inclusive and innovative circular practices in public libraries, and contributes to a **sustainable, inclusive, and creative European circular economy**. It sets the foundation for continuous learning, adaptive management, and long-term replication of the *make-a-thek* model in public libraries worldwide.

1. Introduction

This Impact and Assessment Plan document presents the project's evaluation and impact assessment framework. This document is the basis for the project's evaluation activities, and contains the following chapters:

- **Chapter 1: Introduction**
- **Chapter 2: The expectations and visions**
Presents the results from the working session at the Kick-Off Meeting in February 2025, where the whole consortium was invited to reconsider the main project objectives. Also presents the motivations and expectations of the pilot libraries, collected during the library Kick-Off Meeting in May 2025.
- **Chapter 3: Project success criteria and indicators**
Introduces an overarching logic model for the make-a-thek project, showing the connection between outputs (KPIs), outcomes and expected impact.
- **Chapter 4: Evaluation instruments**
Presents the main quantitative and qualitative evaluation instruments make-a-thek aims to apply to collect the data required to populate the indicator framework.
- **Chapter 5: Ethics**
Discusses ethical considerations of evaluation and impact assessment in make-a-thek.
- **Chapter 6: Timeline**
Provides a short overview of evaluation activities along the three project phases.
- **Chapter 7: Summary and outlook**
Presents the upcoming activities of the evaluation and impact assessment work package.
- **References**

2. The expectations and visions

2.1. Consortium vision and expectations

The starting point: During the Kick-Off Meeting that was convened face-to-face in February 2025 in Brussels, all make-a-thek consortium members were actively involved in the discussion of project motivations, expectations, and visions. Pictures from the session are presented in Fig 01.

Figure 01: Expectations and visions of the make-a-thek consortium, collected during the kick-off meeting in February 2025

2.1.1 Expectations for the *make-a-thek* Project

The *make-a-thek* project envisions a collaborative, inclusive, and inspiring ecosystem that supports circular economy practices within the realms of fashion and craft, anchored in public libraries with makerspaces. Key expectations include:

Strong Collaboration & Communication: Emphasis on mutual collaboration across work packages (WPs), open and honest communication, and clear strategic planning. Partners aim to inspire one another and foster a culture of transparency and shared purpose.

Community & Network Building: A central goal is to transform pilot initiatives into a sustainable network of fashion- and craft-oriented libraries, while also creating connections with craftspersons, makers, and relevant stakeholders at local, national, and international levels, including beyond European borders.

Inclusivity & Accessibility: The project seeks to ensure meaningful participation by embedding inclusivity and accessibility from the outset. This includes developing inclusive pilots, strategies for inclusive spaces, and making content and tools usable for a wide variety of audiences, including those typically underrepresented.

Circular Economy & Sustainability: There is a strong commitment to co-creating positive experiments and tangible business cases in the regional circular economy. The project will showcase successful pilots, support evidence-based impact, and encourage civic engagement at the local level to promote fairer fashion and sustainable practices.

Education & Empowerment: A key output will be joyful and adaptable learning materials, for online and offline experiences, to inspire makers, designers, and prosumers. The project will serve as a source of inspiration for entrepreneurs and creatives, helping participants transform their passion into sustainable ventures.

Visibility & Impact: The project expects to deliver meaningful internal and external communication, including impactful marketing and storytelling around pilot successes. It will leverage its strong network and communication expertise to expand reach and support long-term adoption of project outcomes.

Tools & Resources: Deliverables such as a modular kit and a publicly accessible repository of circular practices will help ensure that knowledge and tools are widely applicable, scalable, and valuable across different settings and communities.

Sustainability & Funding: Raising additional funding through external partnerships (e.g., local library networks) is seen as a pathway to long-term sustainability and scaling of the initiative after the project funding.

In essence, *make-a-thek* aims to be more than a project: it aspires to be a movement that blends creativity, sustainability, and inclusiveness through hands-on learning, shared knowledge, and community empowerment.

2.1.2 Vision for the *make-a-thek* Project

The long-term vision of *make-a-thek* is to spark a global shift in how communities engage with fashion, crafts, sustainability, and shared spaces—starting with experimentation in public libraries across Europe and extending far beyond.

In detail the collection of project partners’ visions can be summarised as follows:

Libraries as Creative Hubs: In the future, public libraries across Europe, and eventually worldwide, will serve as vibrant spaces for craft, fashion design, co-creation, and repair. They will be equipped with makerspaces and supported by local maker communities, enabling people to do things like repair clothing, learn new skills, and collaborate creatively.

A Scalable, Global Movement: The *make-a-thek* approach aims to evolve into a globally recognized methodology, empowering communities on all continents to reconnect with craft heritage and promote sustainable lifestyles. A strong, cooperative network of locations and communities rooted in public libraries and makerspaces will act as a backbone of this movement.

Cultural and Social Transformation: The project envisions a deep cultural shift: from fast fashion to shared, communal design; from consumption to creativity; from exclusion to inclusion. Makerspaces and fablabs will act as “third spaces” within urban infrastructure, reflecting the diversity of our communities and providing equal access to tools, knowledge, and opportunities.

Empowering People and Stories: A central part of the vision is that *make-a-thek* participants, especially those from underrepresented backgrounds, will tell their own stories and shape the movement. The project will highlight the social impact of action, not just economic success, by fostering inclusive and community-driven innovation.

Aligned with Broader European Values: The initiative contributes to the vision of the New European Bauhaus, promoting a greener, more inclusive, and sustainable Europe where arts, culture, and crafts are no longer seen as secondary sectors but as powerful drivers of societal transformation.

A New System for a Circular Society: In ten years, *make-a-thek* envisions its approach integrated into the very fabric of the 15-minute city, with libraries as key nodes in a circular, community-driven economy. These programs will support sustainable local economies, bio-circular business models, and democratized access to technology

and innovation.

A Legacy That Continues: Ultimately, the vision is not only to implement make-a-thek successfully but to inspire future projects that build on its foundation, ensuring its legacy and continued evolution.

An overview of these expectations is shown in Figure 02 together with the vision partners have for make-a-thek.

Figure 02: Summary of expectations and visions of the consortium partners

2.2. The expectations of pilot libraries

During the Kick-Off Meeting for pilot libraries that was convened online in May 2025, members of the pilot libraries were actively involved in the discussion of their project motivations and expectations (see Figure 03).

Figure 03: Motivation and expected outcomes of pilot libraries, collected during the pilot kick-off in May 2025

The results show that these expectations and motivations are closely aligned with the consortium’s expectations. Libraries wish to use the make-a-thek activities to:

- **Establish connections across communities**, between different cultural and age groups, between library and fashion community
- **Position libraries as a key actor in sustainable fashion and circular economy**, as an attractive makerspace, as an open community space
- **Learn how to build up a makerspace and how to apply circular approaches to fashion**
- **Collaborate with and learn from other libraries in the European network**

In the following visualisation (Figure 04) we highlighted the aspects that are especially relevant for libraries.

Figure 04: The pilot libraries most relevant expectations and visions matched with those of the consortium partners

3. Project success criteria and indicator framework

The collection of overarching expectations defined is one starting point of evaluation, as we need to currently revisit the defined expectations and visions to see if our approach can help to reach them and how we can bring evidence for it. The second starting point are the described project activities and KPIs of the Grant Agreement of make-a-thek. To show how these contribute to reaching overarching impacts, we make use of the logic model (Kurz & Kubek, 2016). This model gives a systematic overview of logical relationships between the project’s activities and results, and includes a formative evaluation — determination of the extent to which the project is on track, and which fine-tuning activities should be implemented—as well as summative evaluation at the end of the project.

The illustration in Figure 5 below shows the basic elements of the logic model, which distinguishes between inputs/resources, activities, outputs, outcomes, and impact:

- inputs/resources: all necessary inputs devoted to realise the project's objectives, such as efforts, material; or equipment
- activities: what the project does with the resources like events, tools, workshops, actions - the activities should bring out the desired change
- outputs: services and products offered by and resulting from the project like the number of services and actions implemented

The activities and outputs are important for the project's outcomes and impact, and for that reason, the progression from the outputs to the outcomes and impact is crucial for the project's success.

Figure 05: Overview of the logic model, adapted from Kurz and Kubek (2016)

For the purpose of the make-a-thek project and regular evaluation reflection meetings with consortium partners, we drafted a simplified matrix, combining the outputs and impacts in one field (see Table 01). As the inputs are in the hands of the project management, this category was left out of the WP matrices, with the focus being on analysing tasks, outputs, outcomes, and impacts. Also, for optimal planning of evaluation activities, a column was included for capturing potential means of data gathering.

Planned activities	Engaged Actors	Expected outcomes/impact	Measures/indicators	Means of data gathering
Develop recommendations	Librarians Makers Experts in fashion and crafts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased understanding of trends, policy frameworks and best practices • Identified needs of the engaged actors • Increased understanding on how to design the MAT approach 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 200 resources mapped • 9 + 3 community activation events hosted • No. of participants in the community activation events • No. of questionnaires and interviews collected • Recommendations informing future steps developed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal reporting • Questionnaire • Interview
Co-Design and disseminate the MAT approach and KIT	Librarians Makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased knowledge on how to set up makerspaces for crafts and fashion amongst librarians • Increased knowledge on how to implement co-design processes amongst librarians • Growing networks for librarians through the co-design process • Improved understanding of the library's own needs and expectations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 9 + 3 co-creation sessions hosted • > 20 stakeholders engaged/session • > 3 MAT technological configurations, for beginner, intermediate and advanced levels • Sharing of the MAT KIT and Guide in at least 5 open repositories • > 1000 unique users viewing or downloading the KIT, OER or Guide 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal reporting • Access statistics • Evaluation of workshops via short questionnaire
Develop training material & conduct training	Librarians Makers Experts in fashion and crafts Citizens	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of enhanced local infrastructure for sustainable education and skills • Increased creative skills of citizens • Enhanced skills related to the circular economy for 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open source WS guide • Train-the-trainer programme: 12 capacity building workshops with people in libraries • 50 OERs created • Mobility and knowledge exchange programme: 24 knowledge and skill sharing exchange activities conducted 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feedback questionnaire • Feedback card • Workshop evaluation grid • Access statistics on OER

		<p>both, citizens and fashion and crafts experts.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increased knowledge on how to set up makerspaces for crafts and fashion amongst librarians <p>Impact:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Bringing circular practices to the broader creative industries ● Establishing libraries as vibrant hubs for knowledge exchange, prototyping, testing, and peer learning, as places for circular practices 		
Prepare and implement the pilots	Librarians Citizens Experts in fashion and crafts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Empowerment of citizens to become prosumers partaking in the circular society. ● Better access for citizens to innovative digital and maker technologies ● New groups in local communities attracted to libraries for circular practices <p>Impact:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● More inclusive avenues for repair and upcycling ● Transforming consumers into active contributors to sustainable fashion and crafts. ● Public libraries as vibrant, inclusive community spaces 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 9 + 3 public libraries trained and equipped through pilots ● > 200 people engaged per pilot ● 12 prototyped ideas ● 12 trialled circular craft and fashion ecosystems topic deep dives ● > 150 standardised feedback from pilot participants ● > 6 success stories of MAT small business's impact ● 500 Feedback forms collected from pilot participants ● > 100 new visitors to participating libraries ● 300 libraries reached globally ● SRL will have been raised from 2 to 5-6 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Internal documentation ● Interviews with engaged actors (librarians, fashion and crafts experts, makers) ● Feedback cards ● Evaluation grids (on site)

		and catalysts for circular innovation in fashion, crafts, and other creative sectors.		
Bustour and international rollout	Libraries Citizens Makers Experts in fashion and crafts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Empowerment of citizens to become prosumers partaking in the circular society. • Access for citizens to innovative digital and maker technologies • New groups in local communities attracted to libraries for circular practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International rollout in 3 cities in the global south • Organisation of the mobile pilot bus tour • 300 libraries reached globally 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal documentation • Interviews with engaged actors (librarians, fashion and crafts experts, makers) • Feedback cards • Evaluation grids (on site)
Communication, dissemination and sustainability	Librarians Citizens Makers Experts in fashion and crafts Political decision makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broad awareness for circular practices in fashion and the role of public libraries as community places amongst citizens. • Awareness for circular practices and the role of libraries amongst policy makers • Supporting a shift towards a new prosumer mindset • Fostering a sense of belonging through a continuous community engagement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • > 12 community meetups with at least 400 people participating in networking activities • > 12 promotional events including press conferences and launch events for pilots • > 6 press releases and at least 30 press articles with media coverage across all project activities • > 50 organisations using Communication campaign toolkit and assets • City-level dialogs in 9 pilot cities (1 policy paper with 12 localised versions, 6 city-level dialogues with policy makers and craftspeople) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal documentation • Access and social media statistics

Table 01: Key activities, stakeholder groups, outputs, outcomes and evaluation instruments

The logic model will be regularly revisited by the whole consortium. During these reflection meetings, we will review the outputs and outcomes, discuss potential means of collecting evidence and adapt the evaluation approach if needed.

Capturing and reacting to unintended consequences and challenges of make-a-thek

While the above framework looks into the expected outputs, outcomes and impacts, there might be unintended positive and negative consequences of our activities. In make-a-thek we think that it's important that evaluation also captures these unintended consequences and potential challenges. Thus the logic model will evolve throughout the project with new indicators and will be adapted accordingly. The open and reflective discussion of challenges is an important source for learning and improving the make-a-thek activities, adapting them to new contexts or circumstances that have not been identified throughout the co-design process. The mixture of evaluation instruments, that have both closed and open questions to the portfolio of involved stakeholder groups, will purposefully capturing these unintended consequences and challenges.

4. Evaluation Instruments

In the project we will use a mixture of qualitative and quantitative evaluation instruments to bring evidence for the expected outputs and outcomes listed in the previous chapter. These instruments are carefully selected, some focusing more on the collection of outputs and intermediate outcomes, while others investigate the longer term effects and transformative potential of make-a-thek.

Internal documentation and reporting

Feeds into: Outputs (numbers and formative feedback for key activities), intermediate outcomes (visibility, awareness, knowledge)

Internal reporting is a key source of evaluation data. It is linked to all key activities in the make-a-thek project, and helps to:

- 1) keep track of the output indicators for all key activities, e.g. number of events, workshops, involved participants, developed prototypes etc.
- 2) collect the experiences of the make-a-thek consortium members involved in the project activities. This can, for instance, be formative feedback on the developed recommendations, guidelines, OERs, events etc. (what worked and what did not), as well as inputs on the perceived benefits (the key impacts for the project and for participants)

With these aims, we foresee the following internal reporting activities:

- Internal documentations sheets: summarising key facts about a make-a-thek activity and the main lessons: e.g. Who was participating in the event? What was the programme? What worked well/not so well? What questions and issues came up? What can we learn related to the MAT approach? These sheets are used for internal reporting of consortium members about e.g. the community activation events and trainings. But also by the pilot libraries to document their make-a-thek events and workshops.
- A spreadsheet for the internal reporting on dissemination and outreach was elaborated by WP9.

String map

Feed into: Outputs (description of involved stakeholder groups)

The string map (see Figure 06 and 07) is an instrument that helps to playfully understand the background of the involved stakeholders during the community activation events. It provides the project with insights on who is interested and participating mostly in our activities. It is used across pilot cities during community activation events.

Figure 06: String map template to be used during community activation

Figure 07: String map in use

Participants' feedback cards

Feed into: Outputs (formative feedback for make-a-thek events and workshops), intermediate outcomes (visibility, knowledge, awareness, networking)

Feedback cards will be dedicated to evaluation of events in a very “lightweight” way (see Figure 08). Such cards will be designed for the events supported by make-a-thek, and will not demand a lot of time and effort for completion. The cards will aim to collect participants' feedback on the potential impacts of their event participation. The questions on the cards will be kept at a general level, with the aim being to use this tool across a large diversity of events supported by make-a-thek, allowing for large numbers of feedback cards to be distributed and collected by the project consortium members and the pilot libraries.

They will be provided in an online version to be translated into the different mother languages used in the pilots and to slightly adapt questions, if needed.

Event Title, Date

Please, take 3 minutes to provide us feedback.

1 Please indicate how much the following statements apply for this event:

The topic of this event is highly relevant for me.

I learned a lot of great things in this event.

I would love to get more engaged in fashion and circularity.

I feel triggered to rather doing fashion than consuming fashion.

Funded by the European Union

2 What did you like best?

3 What kind of support is needed to get more involved in fashion and circular economy?

4 Should we stay in contact?

Email: _____

Thank you for your feedback!

Figure 08: Feedback card template to be used for event evaluation

Participants' questionnaires

Feeds into: Outputs (formative feedback for make-a-thek events, trainings and workshops), intermediate outcomes (increased interest, knowledge gains, networking)

These questionnaires will aim to collect more detailed feedback from event, training, and workshop participants, including formative feedback and the benefits experienced by participants in make-a-thek events. As these two-pager questionnaires require two to three minutes of the respondent's time, they are designed for events where make-a-thek has the opportunity to distribute them to

participants and then collect them again. Questionnaires are distributed directly at the end of an event, training, workshop - online or in paper-and-pen version - to collect immediate feedback from participants. This tool can also sometimes be applied for online events, training or workshops.

These evaluations of events, trainings and workshops will collect:

1) formative input: such as the set-up, timing, speakers

2) input on the participants' intermediate benefits: e.g. perceived usefulness and applicability of the content discussed during the event/training/workshop; increases in knowledge and skills; intention to apply the shared knowledge, materials, resources; interest in follow-up with additional activities; and perceived networking opportunities.

As make-a-thek events, training, and workshops cover a broad range of topics, questions will be tailored to the activity in question- while at the same time trying to keep a certain homogeneity in key thematic areas of the questions, so as to allow for comparability between events.

Participants' target evaluation

Feeds into: Outputs (formative feedback for material, trainings and workshops), intermediate outcomes (e.g. increased interest, knowledge gains, networking)

The “target evaluation” (see Figure 09) serves to collect feedback of participants in a make-a-thek training, workshop or event. It consists of a prepared “dart board” design on a poster or flipchart, where each section stands for a specific evaluation item related to the event, workshop or training. Participants are asked to score the item, the best being closest to the bullseye, the worst being furthest away. This evaluation format can be used for online and offline events. It takes only very little time for participants and provides event organisers with the occasion to collect quick feedback, visible for all participants, also as a source for a collaborative final reflection exercise at the end of an event.

Figure 09: Target evaluation template to be used for event evaluation

Participants' graffiti wall/table

Feeds into: Outputs (formative feedback for material, trainings and workshops), intermediate outcomes (e.g. awareness, knowledge gains, networking)

This is a very open format of collecting participants' experiences, opinions, ideas and thoughts during or after a make-a-thek activity. It consists of a big paper, which is put on a wall or table, and is the place for participants to openly share their thoughts. Feedback can be steered into a specific direction by writing some key questions e.g.: What did you enjoy? What do you want to do next? This easy to use evaluation format can also be used as an online version. Miro or Padlet could be examples for collaborative tools that let people simply share their thoughts on a wall.

Figure 10: Graffiti table during community engagement in Barcelona

Impact interviews

Feeds into: Intermediate outcomes (e.g. knowledge gains, awareness for circular practices in fashion, perceived motivations) and expected long-term outcomes (e.g. changing to a prosumer behaviour, applying circular practices)

One of the main evaluation data collection methods in make-a-thek will be semi-structured Impact interviews. The make-a-thek evaluation team will use this technique to investigate intermediate and long-term effects of the project on individuals, who are involved in the make-a-thek activities, to understand which circumstances and contexts influence the generated impact for these individual participants and how individual impacts can spill over to local communities and broader networks of people.

These semi-structured Impact interviews will be guided by a set of question guidelines (an interview protocol) covering the main aspects under investigation. These guidelines support the interviewer's need to cover certain topics, and provide a framework of orientation to ensure comparability of interviews. The guidelines include ideas for questions guiding towards individual topics as well as pre formulated questions to start discussions. These initial questions are broadly formulated and function “like an empty page which is filled out by the interviewee in his or her own words, structured in his or her own way” (Witzel, 2000). Narrative elements of the interview allow the interviewee to determine what is relevant for them. Through this, initial concepts that are reflected in the question

guidelines are refined and enriched by the interviewee (in a form that generates empirical data for project evaluation purposes).

The Impact interviews will be conducted online or face-to-face, and will be audio-recorded for later transcription (if agreed upon by the interviewee). If an interview is not recorded, interviewers will take notes and prepare detailed protocols to replace the transcript. Whether recording permission is granted or not, memory minutes will also be written by the interviewers directly after the interview, so as to keep a record of the topics discussed, of situative and non-verbal aspects of the interview, and topics and ideas which can inform data analysis and subsequent interviews later interpretations. For the transcription and translation of data-sources from the pilot languages to English, AI tools might be used.

For analysis of the interview data, the evaluation team will conduct qualitative content analysis of the transcripts as proposed by Mayring (2000). The applied method is a technique of summarisation, whereby categories are created in an inductive procedure by reducing, paraphrasing and generalising relevant text passages using software such as MAXQDA¹ or Nvivo². The central aspect of the employed technique is to develop categories resembling the original data as closely as possible.

Focus group discussions

Feeds into: Outputs (formative feedback for material, trainings and workshops), intermediate outcomes (e.g. awareness, knowledge gains, networking) and expected long term outcomes (e.g. sustainable practices established in libraries, changing to a prosumer behaviour)

Focus group discussions are moderated group discussions on a certain topic with several participants (Mayring, 2002). The method is widely applied in qualitative research and is considered as a sort of group interview, where a semi-structured approach guides the group discussion while also relying on the responses themselves to move the discussion along. The method is used for an explorative approach to reveal opinions, needs, and interests of the interviewed groups. This method can potentially serve as the principal data source for understanding the outputs and outcomes of mAKE from the perspective of various target groups. Focus group discussions can be supplemented with, or be supplementary to, other sources of data, such as the other sources outlined in this chapter.

In comparison to one-on-one interviews, focus groups have the advantage of allowing the interviewers to observe interactions on a topic, and to experience similarities and differences in participants' opinions directly, instead of deriving them from analyses of separate statements from individual interviewees (Morgan, 2011).

¹ <https://www.maxqda.com/de/>

² <https://www.nvivo.de/>

In recent years, there has been increased use of online focus groups, which provide the advantage of participants being able to take part from a range of locations. One comparison between traditional in person and online focus groups found that the content of the data generated in both formats was remarkably similar (Woodyatt, Finneran and Stephenson, 2016). For sensitive topics, online focus groups might even foster a dynamic whereby participants can open up more than they would in person. Given make-a-thek’s international setting, online focus groups are likely to be a valuable tool for the evaluation team’s collection of data.

Societal readiness level

In order to reflect and monitor the make-a-thek pathway to impact, the project adopts a social innovation impact model – the [Societal Readiness Levels \(SRL\)](#) developed by the Innovation Fund Denmark – to assess the level of societal acceptance of a certain technology, product, process, or intervention ([Bruno et al. 2020](#), Table 02). This approach follows the belief that all innovations are socially relevant and any innovation, be it technical or social, needs to be integrated into the societal environment. Similar to the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) scale, the SRL has 9 levels. It is technology neutral and equally valid as the TRL maturity model, while not contradicting or overlapping with it, as it puts the focus on the societal adaptation of an innovation. make-a-thek will use this scale to observe the societal acceptance of the make-a-thek approach. We depart from SRL 2 with the formulation of proposed solution concepts and potential impacts through the needs mapping and co-creation that takes place at the beginning of the project and expect to increase to SRL 4-5 through the sharing of the piloted solutions and developed policy recommendations. The SRLs will be collaboratively discussed amongst consortium partners at regular time-points of the project but also with external stakeholders involved in our project.

Maturity Level	Description and proposed indicators for evaluation
SRL1	Identification of the generic societal need and associated readiness aspects, <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Specific need(s) identified and described ● Drivers and barriers identified ● Description of stakeholders and their expectations ● No. of stakeholders involved in needs identification
SRL2	Formulation of proposed solution concept and potential impacts; appraisal of societal readiness issues; identification of relevant stakeholders for the development of the solution <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Proposed solution(s) identified and described ● Drivers and barriers conceptually addressed ● Expected impacts per solution co-defined ● Stakeholders identified and contacted for development of solution(s)
SRL3	Initial sharing of the proposed solution with relevant

	<p>stakeholders (e.g. through visual mock-ups): a limited group of the society knows the solution or similar initiatives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No. of co-creation workshops with stakeholders • No. of stakeholders involved in workshops • Feedback collected and documented from stakeholders • Solution(s) communicated across partner networks
SRL4	<p>Solution validated through pilot testing in controlled environments to substantiate proposed impacts and societal readiness: a limited group of the society tests the solution or similar initiatives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No. of pilots in controlled environments implemented • No. of stakeholders involved in the pilots • Formative and summative feedback collected from stakeholders
SRL5	<p>Solution validated through pilot testing in real or realistic environments and by relevant stakeholders: the society knows the solution or similar initiatives but is not aware of their benefits</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No. of pilots in real environments implemented • No. of stakeholders involved in the pilots • Formative and summative feedback collected from stakeholders • Solution communicated to society via widely spread media
SRL6	<p>Solution demonstrated in real world environments and in co-operation with relevant stakeholders to gain feedback on potential impacts: the society knows the solution or similar initiatives and awareness of their benefits increases</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wider roll-out and adoption of the solution by other stakeholders • Communication of solution and benefits to a broad audience
SRL7 (beyond project scope)	<p>Refinement of the solution and, if needed, retesting in real world environments with relevant stakeholders: the society is completely aware of the solution's benefits, a part of the society starts to adopt similar solutions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No. of adopted similar solutions across Europe • No. of refinements implemented and retested
SRL8 (beyond project scope)	<p>Targeted solution, as well as a plan for societal adaptation, complete and qualified; society is ready to adopt the solution and have used similar solutions on the market</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overall societal awareness of the benefits and implemented solutions • Solution roll-out planned with additional stakeholders, financial sources, communication plans etc.
SRL9 (beyond project scope)	<p>Actual solution proven in relevant societal environments after launch on the market; the society is using the solution</p>

	available on the market <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solution is a widely accepted practice across Europe
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Table02: Societal readiness level (Bruno et al. 2020)

Organisational readiness levels

With the organisational readiness levels, inspired by [Bruno et al. 2020](#), we look at the results of the make-a-thek efforts and their broader effects within the perimeter of the libraries implementing them. In this concept key impact areas span from professional roles, competencies and skills to organisational functions, processes and physical infrastructures that are influenced by the innovation (see Table 03). The ORLs 1-2 match SRLs 1-2 in reflecting the growing awareness about the existence of an organisational readiness issue required for make-a-thek. In turn, ORLs 3-6 are concerned with the more and more extended consideration of roles, processes, functions and structures (and governance systems) in the phases of testing, validation and demonstration of the targeted outputs of our project. ORL 7 matches both SRL 7 and TRL 7 in its being referred to the final stage of prototyping of the complete solution, while ORLs 8-9 belong to the pre-market and market launch phase, meeting the prerequisite of organisational readiness in full.

In make-a-thek we have libraries covering different levels of expertise, familiarity with circularity, and proximity to library services involved in our pilot activities. Given these differences their might also be differences in organisational maturity levels that we will detect throughout the project. But in general we expect to move from an ORL 2-3 when starting the project to an ORL 5-6 at the end, which will be assessed together with the participating pilot libraries.

Maturity Level	Description
ORL1	Identification of the organizational need (infrastructures, capabilities, skills) and associated organisational readiness aspects <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specific need(s) identified and described • Drivers and barriers identified • Description of stakeholders and their expectations • No. of stakeholders involved in needs identification
ORL2	Formulation of proposed solution concept and potential impacts; appraisal of organisational readiness issues; identification of relevant roles, processes, functions and structures for the solution <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proposed solution(s) identified and described • Drivers and barriers conceptually addressed • Expected impacts per solution co-defined

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders identified and contacted for development of solution(s) • Roles, processes, functions and structures identified
ORL3	<p>Comprehensive description of proposed solution's impacts within the organisation in terms of roles, competences and skills, physical infrastructures required</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Roles, processes, functions and structures described • Required competences and skills described • Required infrastructure and technical requirements identified
ORL4	<p>Solution validated through simulation of major induced changes to substantiate proposed impacts and organisational readiness: the organisation which is developing the solution starts to acquire roles, competences and skills, physical infrastructures required</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Roles, processes, functions and structures are starting to be adapted to the solution • Concrete competences and skills acquired • Infrastructures and technical requirements implemented
ORL5	<p>Proposed solution validated through pilot testing in real or realistic organisational environments: the organisation which is developing the solution achieves roles, competences and skills, physical infrastructures required</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No. of pilots in real environments implemented • No. of stakeholders involved in the pilots • Formative and summative feedback collected from stakeholders • Skills and competences, roles, processes and infrastructures are tested for fit for purpose
ORL6	<p>Solution demonstrated in real world environments and in co-operation with relevant stakeholders to gain feedback in order to improve roles, processes, functions and infrastructures required</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solution implemented in real world environments • Formative and summative feedback collected from stakeholders • Required adaptations in roles, processes, functions and infrastructures defined and implemented • Required adaptations of skills and competences defined
ORL7 (beyond project scope)	<p>Refinement of the roles, processes, functions and infrastructures required and retesting of the solution in relevant organisational environments</p>
ORL8 (beyond project scope)	<p>Targeted solution, as well as a plan for organisational embedment, complete and qualified: roles, processes, functions and infrastructures are available</p>

ORL9 (beyond project scope)	Actual solution proven in relevant organisational environments: roles, processes, functions and infrastructures are correctly used for the solution on the marke
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Table03: Organisational readiness level (Bruno et al. 2020)

5. Ethics

make-a-thek is committed to open science practices and transparency while at the same time adhering to strict data management rules, particularly when it comes to personal data. During the evaluation and impact assessment activities described in this document, personal data will be collected from participants during administration of feedback cards, questionnaires, interviews, focus group discussions, and possible other encounters during make-a-thek events, training and workshops. Accordingly, make-a-thek has e.g. created informed consent, anonymity and confidentiality protocols that will be employed during evaluation activities, as well as a secure, password-protected, cloud-based data management system to manage data storage and, where necessary, data-sharing among consortium members (with the necessary anonymity and confidentiality measures for certain kinds of data).

The informed consent template can be found in the Annex of this document.

More details on mAkE’s ethical approach and data management instruments can be found in the Project Handbook (Deliverable D1.1) and the Data Management Plan (Deliverable D1.2).

6. Timeline

In make-a-thek evaluation and impact assessment started from the onset of the project and will accompany all project activities and the three project phases (see Figure 10) until the project end.

Figure 11: make-a-thek project phases

In **phase 1**, the co-creation phase, the focus of evaluation lays on the definition of expectations and objectives of the involved stakeholders that are the basis for evaluating the project impact in a later stage. We co-create impact metrics for the capacity building events and materials, as well as for the evaluation of pilot activities.

In **phase 2**, during the implementation of make-a-thek in the pilot libraries, evaluation will emphasize on the collection of feedback from the involved citizens, makers, fashion experts and librarians. This is the project period where we learn if the implementation of make-a-thek approach and capacity building impacts the different stakeholder groups as expected. We will also understand unexpected outcomes of our activities and gather a rich set of learnings from the implementation of make-a-thek in the pilot libraries, but also by evaluating the engagement via the make-a-thek bus.

In **phase 3**, evaluation and impact assessment will support the understanding, how far the developed make-a-thek resources and approach can help to scale circular fashion activities in public libraries in locations outside of Europe. With this aim we will again collect input from the involved citizens, makers, fashion experts and librarians. And we will accompany the city level dialogues and the dissemination of policy briefs to enrich impact assessment with the feedback of political decision makers.

7. Summary and outlook

Evaluation and impact assessment is key to proof that our make-a-thek project and all conducted activities contribute to the clear project vision and expectations

of the involved stakeholders. Thus this impact assessment plan serves as a basis to document outputs, outcomes and impacts of make-a-thek. It consists of a number of clearly defined KPIs and expected outcome metrics that follow the logic-model approach and are the basis for regular reflection within the consortium. The plan also introduces a first set of quantitative and qualitative evaluation instruments that help to collect data related to these impact metrics and a timeline when to apply these instruments throughout the project runtime.

In the coming project months the collection of evaluation data will be at the focus of the evaluation team. With this aim, we will organise training sessions related to impact assessment for the involved pilot libraries and regular reflection sessions to discuss not only the evaluation process but also first outcomes that could inform an adaptive management. We will also collect data on the community structures and indicators for networking and community building effects and specifically focus on engagement strategies, degree of involvement, relevant support mechanisms and material, recognition of the approach by relevant stakeholders, and document benefits and possible negative effects of the suggested approach. The first lessons learned will be presented in D11.1 Interim Impact Assessment Report, due in project month 24 (31st of October 2026).

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Annex

Informed Consent Form

Informed Consent Form

This informed consent form is for participants in the innovation action titled: "make-a-thek "

[make-a-thek partner: insert name of main contact person]

[make-a-thek partner: insert the name of your organisation]

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101177660

This Informed Consent Form has two parts:

- Information Sheet (to share information about the study with you)
- Certificate of Consent (for signatures if you agree)

You will be given a copy of the full Informed Consent Form

Information Sheet

Introduction

I am [redacted], and I work at [redacted] organisation in [redacted]. I am working on some research and innovation actions which are setting up creative maker spaces in public libraries to explore circular fashion, traditional crafts, and local innovation.

Purpose

make-a-thek is an EU funded project that brings modular, easy-to-replicate makerspaces into public libraries. These spaces focus on fashion and crafts, offering open access to innovative and circular approaches to making and design.

Through community co-creation, the project will develop a practical toolkit and open educational resources (OERs) to help libraries set up their own fashion- and craft-focused makerspaces.

The project will pilot these ideas in at least 12 libraries (9 in Europe, 3 internationally), where communities will explore how to combine traditional heritage crafts with modern digital tools like 3D printing and laser cutting. This approach supports sharing sustainable skills and cultural knowledge. A mobile makerspace in the form of a bus is also planned, enabling flexible workshops and activities in different regions, especially rural regions.

The long term goals of the project are to

- Empower a new generation of prosumers—people who both create and use in sustainable ways.
- Position libraries as hubs for circular making and knowledge-sharing.
- Preserve heritage crafts through digital innovation.
- Foster circular and green innovation in fashion and crafts.

Type of Intervention

(please select)

Questionnaire

Focus group

Co-design workshop

Interview

Selection of Participants

make-a-thek aims to create meaningful connections between libraries, and local communities of makers, fashion and craftspeople, citizens and prosumers and will engage these stakeholders during the course of the project. All stakeholders participate actively in the project supporting research activities, such as surveys, interviews, and workshops. We ensure the values, rights, and interests of all.

Voluntary Participation

Your participation is completely voluntary and you stop your participation at any time.

Procedure

(chose from the examples, depending on what activity you involve the person in)

1) the following applies only to co-design sessions or workshops:

You will take part in a co-design session/workshop with a mix of other participants. This design process will be guided by [give the name of moderator]. The whole co-design process will be documented and the documentation material will be shared amongst the make-a-thek partners. Personal information about you will not be shared in any form beyond the consortium partners unless explicitly agreed in advance.

The co-design session/workshop will take place in [location of the group discussion].

2) the following applies only to interviews:

You will participate in an interview with [name of interviewer]. The interview is conducted with the following aim: _____

If you do not wish to answer any of the questions during the interview, you may say so and we will move on to the next question. The information recorded is confidential, and no one else except [name of person(s) with access to the information] will have access to the information documented during your interview.) [The recordings will be destroyed after _____ period of time.]

3) the following applies only to questionnaire surveys and should be added as a header:

You will fill out a questionnaire which will be provided by [name of a distributor of blank questionnaires] and collected by [name of a collector of completed questionnaires].

If you do not wish to answer some of the questions included in the questionnaire, you may skip them and move on to the next question. The information recorded is confidential, and no one else except [name of person(s) with access to the information] will have access to her questionnaire. [The questionnaires will be destroyed after _____ period of time.]

Reimbursements

You will not be provided with any payment to take part in the project activities. Material for the make-a-thek activities will be provided by the project as far as this is within our budgetary limits. If material is needed that cannot be covered by the project budget, we will inform you beforehand. Snacks are also provided by the project.

Confidentiality

We will not be sharing information about you outside of the project team. The information that we collect from this project will be kept confidential. Information about you that will be collected from the research will be put away and no-one but the researchers will be able to see it. Any information about you will be stored

anonymously. Non-personal data extracted from the different activities you will be involved in will be shared with the make-a-thek consortium in an anonymous manner and stored on a secure server. Any research results resulting from the analysis of your data will be presented in an aggregated form and cannot be traced back to you.

(The following text may apply for co-design sessions & workshops discussions): We will ask you and others in the group not to talk to people outside the group about what was said within the group. We will, in other words, ask each participant to keep what was said in the group confidential.

Benefits of Participation

You may benefit from your participation in make-a-thek in various ways, depending on your personal interests and role as a participant. Overall, make-a-thek strengthens the local infrastructure for circular economy, crafts and sustainable fashion by offering new spaces and activities in public libraries and beyond.

Sharing of Research Findings

We will be sharing what we have learned with the participants and with the community. We will do this by providing a written report, which will not include your personal data. Rather, the findings will be reported in a general and aggregated form to ensure that you personally cannot be identified. Nothing that you will tell us today will be shared with anybody outside the research team and nothing will be attributed to you by name. We might also publish the results in academic outlets in order that other interested people may learn from our research. Data will only be included in these publications in aggregated and anonymized form.

Right to refuse or withdraw

You may choose to opt-out and stop your participation at any time.

Whom to Contact

If you have any questions you may ask them now or later, even after the participation. If you wish to ask questions later, you may contact any of the following: [name, address/telephone number/e-mail]

This proposal has been reviewed and approved by the European Union's research and innovation programme Horizon Europe, including an ethical screening to make sure that participants are protected from harm and their privacy is respected at all times.

Certificate of Consent

I have read the foregoing information, or it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions that I have asked have been answered to my satisfaction.

I hereby give consent for my data to be conveyed and documented for the purpose stated above. I confirm that I have been informed of the nature of make-a-thek and that my participation is voluntary. I am aware that I may withdraw my consent at any time.

Print Name of Participant _____

Signature of Participant _____

Date _____

Day/month/year

Statement by the project team member/person taking consent

I have accurately read out the information sheet to the participant, and to the best of my ability made sure that the person understands the process.

I confirm that the participant was given an opportunity to ask questions about the study, and all the questions asked by him/her have been answered correctly and to the best of my ability. I confirm that the individual has not been coerced into giving consent, and the consent has been given freely and voluntarily.

Print Name of project team member/person taking the consent

Signature of project team member/person taking the consent

Date _____

Day/month/year

A copy of this Informed Consent Form has been provided to the participant